

REFORMS MADE IN THE FIELD OF ECONOMY DURING THE ATATÜRK PERIOD (ATATÜRK DÖNEMİ İKTISAT ALANINDA YAPILAN ISLAHATLAR) ÖZ

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From 1923 to the present, different economic policies have been implemented in Turkey. We can classify the economic policies of the Atatürk era as liberal economic policies from the foundation of the Republic in 1923 until the world economic crisis in 1929, and central economic policies from 1930 until Atatürk's death in 1938. When the new Turkish state was founded in 1920, a very weak economic legacy was inherited from the Ottoman Empire. In such an environment, the War of Independence would be fought with limited resources. In order to become a fully independent country, Atatürk first emphasized economic independence. For this purpose, an Economic Congress was held in Izmir to take certain economic measures and put them into practice as soon as possible. This congress was the first economic conference held in the economic field during the Republic of Turkey and has an important position in the adoption of the mixed economic model.

Ataturk always advocated the development of a planned economy. The best example of this is the convening of the economic congress before the declaration of the republic and the decisions taken regarding the formation of the state economic policy. After the establishment of the republic, breakthroughs were made in many areas such as agriculture, industry, transportation, banking, foreign trade, etc. If necessary, foreign experts were invited and their opinions were listened to and training was provided to practitioners in these areas. During Ataturk's period, the Turkish lira maintained its value and showed an inflation-free development. During this period, all remaining debts of the Ottoman Empire were paid. Laws were enacted and banks were established to encourage agriculture, industry and trade. In short, the country took various measures to be self-sufficient and prevent external dependency and experienced a rapid development process.

ABSTRACT

From 1923 to the present, different economic policies have been implemented in Turkey. We can classify the economic policies of the Atatürk era as liberal economic policies from the foundation of the Republic in 1923 until the world economic crisis in 1929, and central economic policies from 1930 until Atatürk's death in 1938. When the new Turkish state was founded in 1920, a very weak economic legacy was inherited from the Ottoman Empire. In such an environment, the War of Independence would be fought with limited resources. In order to become a fully independent country, Atatürk first emphasized economic independence. For this purpose, an Economic Congress was held in Izmir to take certain economic measures and put them into practice as soon as possible. This congress was the first economic conference held in the economic field during the Republic of Turkey and has an important position in the adoption of the mixed economic model.

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Giriş

Despite various reforms aimed at strengthening and modernizing the Ottoman Empire, these activities could not prevent the collapse of the Ottoman Empire. Although these activities did not achieve their goal, they paved the way for the establishment of the Republic of Turkey (Kodaman, 2007).

In the early years of the Republic, economic conditions were not good. When Atatürk founded the Republic of Turkey, he had to deal with problems such as rebuilding the destruction left by the war, modernizing fiscal policy, regulating the tax system, nationalizing natural monopolies, most of which were in the hands of foreigners, and the need to establish a central bank (Akalin, 2008, p.11). Activities aimed at solving these problems and reshaping economic policy were; organizing the Izmir Economic Congress, abolishing the tithe tax, starting the nationalization of the economy, establishing the banking system and the central bank, and carrying out reforms such as reorganizing the tax system.

It is observed that during the Ataturk period, attempts were made to initiate economic structuring and long-term development initiatives. Therefore, in order for the long-term development of an economy to be successful, the economic structure must be based on a solid institutional foundation. This study aims to examine the policies related to economic reforms during the Ataturk period.

Fiscal Policy

Reforms such as the Izmir Economic Congress, the abolition of the tithe tax, nationalizations, the 1929 World Great Depression, the establishment of central banks, tax system reforms, statism and the financing of planned development by the treasury are important in the restructuring of fiscal policy during the Atatürk period (Akalin, 2008, p.10).

Two different fiscal policies were followed during the Atatürk period. In the literature, the fiscal policies of the Atatürk period are divided into two periods as 1923-1929 and 1929-1938. The Republic of Turkey inherited an economically difficult period from the Ottoman Empire. According to the decisions of the Izmir Economic Congress, the Republic of Turkey was required to make rapid development efforts and follow liberal policies. However, due to the negative effects of the Great Depression in 1929 on the world economy and the fact that the decisions taken in the Izmir Economic Congress on issues such as industry, capital, etc. did not yield the desired results, state-centered policies were followed during the 1929-1938 period (Kahraman & Şişmanoğlu, 2019, p.635).

The fiscal policies followed by Atatürk were to care about the economic, social and political conditions of the period, to take care to participate in economic policies and to implement the necessary policies that would benefit the country's interests. It is seen that in the 1923-1929 period, he revived the social and economic life of the country by implementing free trade conditions, and in the 1929-1938 period, he tried to eliminate the negative effects of the global crisis and accelerate the industrialization process in order to increase state intervention and public investments (Vural, 2008, pp.109-110).

The main goal of the fiscal policies implemented during the Atatürk period was the modernization of the tax system (Vural, 2008, p.77). The Republican government implemented reforms related to the taxes it inherited from the Ottoman Empire. Tax reforms were implemented with the abolition of the tithe tax in 1925 and the implementation of some new tax laws in 1926-1927. In 1924, in order to reduce the burden on the agricultural sector, the tithe tax, which constituted 28.5% of the budget revenues, was abolished and new taxes were introduced to support the country's financial needs. The government was also affected by the financial crisis experienced after 1930 due to the Great Depression that affected the world. During the process, some new tax practices were introduced for the payment of civil servant and worker salaries (Akdağ, Sarı, 2020, p.197-198).

Izmir Economic Congress

The economic policies to be implemented by the newly established Republic were determined by the Izmir Economic Congress. In addition, a call was made for the integration of the public and political sectors at the congress.

"This congress is comprehensive and allows people from all segments of society to participate. In order to ensure this participation, it was decided to send 8 people from each district in accordance with the

legislation. The composition of these eight people is as follows: a businessman, a tradesman, a worker, a company, a bank and three farmer representatives." (Ülken, 1994, p.40).

Atatürk convened the Izmir Economic Congress eight months before the foundation of the Republic in order to determine the preferences of the masses in forming economic policies (Ülken, 2011, p.29).

The leader and convener of the congress, Gazi Mustafa Kemal Pasha, made an impressive speech and stated that the economy should be taken very seriously as a factor determining the future of the nation and the state, and that the failure to take economic measures in the development of the Ottoman state led to the final result (Taşdurmaz, 2002, p.52).

Long before the foundation of the Republic, the first Turkish Economic Congress was held in Izmir on February 17, 1923. Representatives from different business circles attended the meeting to discuss the economic situation, the measures to be taken and the work to be done. Speaking here, Atatürk said, "No matter how great the political and military victory is, if it is not supported by economic victory, the success achieved cannot be sustainable and permanent." He resolutely emphasized that we must first give importance to our economy in order for the new Turkey to gain the power it deserves. With this sentence, he clearly expressed the importance of the economy for the new Turkish state and all countries. As a result of the discussions held within the framework of this Congress regarding the current situation and future of the Turkish economy, the national economic principles called "Economic Pact" were accepted, considering the opportunities and needs of Turkey at that time. According to the principles of the national economy, it was envisaged that it would rely on its own power and resources in order to develop without being restricted by external powers. At the same time, it was decided to nationalize the enterprises owned by foreign companies through state purchases in order to prevent economic alienation. In addition, according to this principle, the establishment of necessary credit institutions and good organizations that will provide financing for economic development is among the targets (Turan et al., 2004, p.217).

As a result, the Congress of Economics envisaged the enactment of the necessary laws and regulations for the revitalization of private enterprise and the provision of infrastructure and technical services such as education, transportation, and communication, as well as government credit opportunities. In short, the congress approved the economic structure inherited from the Ottoman Empire with a nationalist understanding and envisaged legal and institutional regulations to make economic activities more efficient (Kepenek, 2009, p.35).

First Five-Year Industrial Plan

BBYSP is a success of statist policies. Due to the success of the application, starting from 1936, a committee consisting of experts in the field prepared the Second Five-Year Industrialization Plan (IBYSP) covering the years 1938-1942. Contrary to the first plan, starting from the breakthroughs in heavy industry, steel, chemistry and machinery, priority was given to the production of intermediate and investment goods and approximately 112 million liras of investment was planned to be made in these areas. (Karakayalı, 2003, p.78).

The essence of BBYSP can be listed under the following three main headings.

1. Industries where basic raw materials are grown domestically or can be supplied domestically in a short time have been addressed.
2. Since these industries are large-scale industries and require technical power, their establishment is the responsibility of the state.
3. The production level of the proposed industry is proportional to the needs and production of the country.

The industries planned to be established in BBYSP are divided into 5 main groups (Karakayalı, 2003, p.77):

1. Knitting (cotton, wool, yarn)
2. Mineral processing plants (steel, coal, copper, sulfur)

3. Paper, pulp and cardboard
4. Chemistry (chlorine, phosphoric acid, rose oil, etc.)
5. Stone and soil (glass, bottles, ceramics, cement)

As its name suggests, BBYSP mainly targets the industrial sector, apart from agriculture and services. Considering that the share of the industrial sector in the gross national product (GNP) was 15% in the 1930s, it was aimed to keep 85% of the economy outside the plan (Özçelik and Tuncel, 2007, p.260).

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The new republic wanted to get rid of the image of an agricultural country. In this context, the strategic goals of the BBYSP can be summarized as follows:

1. The main purpose is to meet basic needs.
2. Care should be taken to meet the raw materials for the proposed industry branch from domestic sources.
3. Reducing external dependency to a minimum level (Karakayalı, 2003, p.78).

Monetary Policy in the Ataturk Period

One of the most important economic policies during the Ataturk era was the protection of the internal and external value of the Turkish lira. Ataturk's permission for emissions as a financing tool was linked to the importance he gave to monetary policy. During the Ataturk era, monetary policy was not inflationary and the external value of the currency was protected. Simple economic theory was not used to prevent the Turkish lira from losing value (Kahraman and Sismanoglu, 2019, pp.636-638).

The main goal of the Republican cadre was to prevent inflation under all circumstances and to maintain price stability and the value of money. The absence of a central bank in the early years of the Republic led to serious restrictions in monetary policy. Because central banks have the ability to directly determine emissions in the economy and to affect, reduce and expand other monetary aggregates that make up the money supply (Yay, 1998, p.292).

In the early years of the foundation of the Republic, strong importance was given to increasing the money supply. The aim was to increase the money supply and ensure public confidence in the Turkish currency. Due to the closed national economic model implemented during this period, the Turkish lira gained significant value, export capacity decreased while import demand increased. While the customs tariffs implemented during this period did not reduce the demand for foreign exchange, external debt repayments were among the factors that increased the demand for foreign exchange. In addition, the stability of the Turkish lira was disrupted during this period due to the impact of the World Economic Depression of 1929, and the Law for the Protection of the Value of Turkish Currency was enacted on February 25, 1930. The law strengthened the state's control over foreign exchange. One of the important developments in monetary policy during the Republic period was the establishment of the Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey on June 30, 1930 (Sarı, 2014).

From the foundation of the Republic until 1929, Turkey followed monetary and fiscal policies with great importance in combating inflation in order to protect the value of the Turkish lira. After the First World War, the Ottoman Bank's right to print money was terminated. According to the agreement made with the Public Debt Administration, 159 million liras worth of banknotes (in seven series) consisting of gold and German treasury bonds were put into circulation from 1915 until the end of the war. In 1922, a fire broke out in Izmir and 30 million banknotes were burned to ashes. Later, the Republic government took over the remaining banknotes and coins worth 8-10 million dollars. Since these coins were not printed at the beginning of the Republic, they were used until 1927 (Eroğlu, 2010, p.27).

The first banknotes of the Republic were put into circulation on December 5, 1927. The banknotes were put into circulation in denominations of 1, 5, 10, 50, 100, 500 and 1000 lira. Since there was no

alphabet revolution at that time, the writings on these coins were printed in Arabic letters and French. The fact that 1,000 lira was equivalent to 1,250 dollars during this period revealed the value of the TL. The first Latin-lettered banknotes were introduced into the market on October 15, 1937 with a 5-lira banknote (Kalaycı, 2010, p.111). The printing of the first coins began on February 12, 1924. Coins with a total value of 2 million lira were printed. (Akgönül, 2001, p.123).

Establishment of the Banking System and the Central Bank in the Atatürk Period

The Republic of Turkey inherited the economically exhausted legacy of the Ottoman Empire, whose economy was largely based on agriculture. The economic policies of this period aimed to change and standardize the policies regarding social and economic structures. The Izmir Economic Congress was held in 1923. In this Congress, it was decided to establish a central commercial bank and private commercial banks affiliated with the bank, and to establish an industrial bank that would provide credit support to industrial enterprises (Doğan, 2012, p.402).

In the Congress where the economic sectors and organizational structures necessary for the development of the country were determined, we see that İş Bankası (1924) and Sanayi Martın Bankası (1925) were established in response to the decisions on banking, industrialization and corporatization. The establishment of the Islamic Bank one year after the foundation of the Republic has been a guide for the organizational structures established in later periods. İş Bankası is important because it is the first organizational structure opened to national development as a private institution (Aydemir, 2020, pp. 207-208). In 1924, banking transactions in the Republic of Turkey were carried out by 17 foreign banks and 16 Turkish banks (such as İtibar-i Milli Bankası and Ziraat Bankası). It is stated that Turkish banks were successful in the 1920s, but they could not completely regain the business of foreign banks (Pıçak et al., 2018, pp. 157-158).

It is known that Atatürk carried out various studies to develop the economy of the Republic of Turkey. In this context, Etibank played an important role in the development of the mining and energy sectors. The bank was established on October 23, 1935 as an economic state institution for the purpose of operating, nationalizing and conducting banking activities in a certain number of mining basins, railways, energy facilities and underground resources under foreign control (Polatoğlu, 2019, pp. 446-449).

Graph 1: Banks Established in the Republic of Türkiye During the Atatürk Period

Kaynak: Bozoklu, 2003.

Conclusion

As Gazi Mustafa Kemal Atatürk said, victory on the battlefield has no meaning on its own. In order for a country to live completely independently and gain an honorable place in the world of nations, economic sovereignty must also be secured and strengthened. Development will be the nation's greatest ideal and goal. It can be said that Atatürk's words, "The foundation of the new Turkish state is not the bayonet, but the economy on which the bayonet is based" are the best reflection of this.

In the first fifteen years of the Republic of Turkey, the state had to always be the pioneer of the economy. When the conditions of the period, the qualified population loss during the war, the inadequacy of inheritance and the Ottoman debt legacy were added to this, the situation became completely inextricable. The inexperience and capital accumulation in the private sector were also among the reasons why the state and statism were necessary. The Great Depression of 1929 was a preparation for protectionist policies and the country determined the mixed economy policy as its basic policy.

The Atatürk era was a period in which important steps were taken towards gaining economic independence for Turkey. Industrialization, modernization in agriculture, correction of monetary and fiscal policies, restructuring of foreign trade and the importance given to education reflect Atatürk's vision of economic development. These reforms laid the foundation for Turkey's economic development in the second half of the 20th century and these strong steps in the early years of the Republic played a major role in shaping today's economic structure.

In conclusion, Atatürk's reforms in the field of economy aimed to ensure the development of Turkey as a modern state and to create an independent economy. The effects of these reforms continue to this day, and Atatürk's economic vision still serves as a guide in the development process of the Republic of Turkey.

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